

Dongfang Special Entangled Spherical Solution of Laplace Equation

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Abstract: The latest discovery of special entangled spherical harmonics indicates that traditional spherical harmonics are only a very narrow partial solution of spherical harmonic partial differential equations, and the theory of exact solutions for similar linear partial differential equations is therefore subject to disruptive effects. Here is a detailed introduction to the special entangled solution of the Laplace equation for the Dirichlet problem in a spherical region. Returning to the analytical form of the solution of spherical harmonic partial differential equations, it is first explained that in the special case where the magnetic quantum is zero, the spherical harmonic function partially degenerates into a Legendre function with respect to the angle θ , resulting in the existence of missing solutions in the Laplace equation. Then provide two special entangled solution sets for the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum number, including sine and cosine functions for angles θ and ϕ . The integral constant of the zero magnetic quantum number general solution in the special case formed by linear superposition of three types of special solution sets is not unique, indicating that the specific form of the exact solution of the Laplace equation cannot be determined. It can be seen that the conclusions of scientific theories described by partial differential equations are not absolutely reliable, and the theory of partial differential equations has serious flaws that urgently need to be improved.

Keywords: Spherical harmonic partial differential equation; Special entangled spherical harmonic function; Laplace equation; Exact solution uncertainty.

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1 Introduction

The Laplace equation^[1-5] is widely used to describe various physical phenomena and engineering techniques^[6-10]. Electromagnetics uses Laplace's equation to describe the distribution of electromagnetic fields; Thermodynamics uses Laplace equation to describe steady-state temperature distribution; The Laplace equation is used in fluid mechanics to describe the steady-state pressure and velocity distribution; The theory of gravity uses the Laplace equation to describe the distribution of the gravitational field; The Laplace equation is used in engineering technology to calculate the dynamic changes of interacting systems; Biology even uses Laplace's equation to describe the laws of motion and development. In fact, the causal relationships and confidence levels of these theories are not reliable in traditional cognition. According to the latest discovery of special entangled spherical harmonics, there are a large number of missing solutions in the spherical harmonic partial differential equations decomposed from the Laplace equation in the spherical coordinate system^[11]. All applications related to the Laplace equation also obviously have missing solutions. The conclusion of the widespread application of the Laplace equation needs to be systematically reprocessed^[12,13]. Here we introduce a special set of solutions to the Laplace equation represented by a special entangled spherical harmonic function that goes beyond the scope described by traditional standard solutions for the special case of zero magnetic quantum numbers.

2 Traditional solution of Laplace equation

In a three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system, the Laplace equation is the simplest symmetric second-order linear partial differential equation satisfied by a time independent function $u = u(x, y, z)$,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

Usually, when dealing with the Laplace equation in a spherical coordinate system, a transformation relationship is introduced between the Cartesian coordinate parameters (x, y, z) and the spherical coordinate parameters (r, θ, ϕ) ,

$$\begin{aligned} x &= r \sin \theta \cos \phi \\ y &= r \sin \theta \sin \phi \\ z &= r \cos \theta \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Thus, the Cartesian coordinate form of Laplace equation (1) is transformed into spherical coordinate form,

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \phi^2} = 0 \quad (3)$$

In history, the Dirichlet condition was proposed

$$u(\theta, \phi)|_{r=R} = f(\theta, \phi) \quad (4)$$

The purpose is to obtain the spherical solution of the Laplace equation, and the additional condition implied by the Dirichlet condition is that the exact solution has no singularities inside the sphere. This implicit condition is worth discussing. If the Laplace equation describes the electromagnetic field of the source inside the sphere, the absence of singularities inside the sphere is actually not true. Therefore, it is not logical to abandon the existence of singularities within the Laplace sphere in advance for the singularity problem. Let's first list the general solution form and then determine the integral constant based on the actual problem.

The solution to the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation (3) given in standard textbooks is

composed of the traditional associated Legendre spherical harmonic function $Y_n(\theta, \phi)^{[14]}$. For any integer n , the expression of the traditional solution's implementable programmatic verification is as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
 u(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \sum_{l=0}^n r^l Y_l(\theta, \varphi) \\
 Y_l(\theta, \varphi) &= \sum_{m=0}^l (a_l^m \cos m\varphi + b_l^m \sin m\varphi) P_l^m(\cos \theta)
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{5}$$

This solution abandons the solution with the coordinate origin as the singularity. If the field source is at the coordinate origin, this traditional solution is unreasonable.

The above form is convenient for memory, but it hides many details, which is not conducive to problem discovery, and therefore limits the innovation and development of theory. (5) The associative Legendre function $P_l^m(\cos \theta)$ in is a polynomial function,

$$P_l^m(\cos \theta) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \underbrace{\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\sin^m \theta \sum_{n=0}^{\frac{l-m+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \frac{(2k-l+m-2)(2k+l+m-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \cos^{2n} \theta \right) \right)}_{l-m=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \underbrace{\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\sin^m \theta \sum_{n=0}^{\frac{l-m+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^n \frac{(2k-l+m-1)(2k+l+m)}{(2k+1)2k} \cos^{2n+1} \theta \right) \right)}_{l-m=1,3,5,\dots} \end{array} \right\}$$

The analytical form of the traditional solution (5) for the Dirichlet problem of Laplace equation containing singular terms is as follows.

Lemma 1 (Traditional Solution of Ball Laplace): If the integer m , natural number l , and positive integer n satisfy the relationship $|m| \leq l$ and $l \leq n$, then the spherical coordinate function

$$u(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{n_1} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\alpha_l r^l + \frac{\alpha_{-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \left(a_{n,l}^{(m)} \cos m\varphi + a_{n,l}^{(-m)} \sin m\varphi \right) \sin^m \theta \right) \times \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l-m+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l+m-2)(2k+l+m-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \cos^{2j} \theta \right) \right)}_{l-m=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{n_2} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\beta_l r^l + \frac{\beta_{-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \left(b_{n,l}^{(m)} \cos m\varphi + b_{n,l}^{(-m)} \sin m\varphi \right) \sin^m \theta \right) \times \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l-m+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l+m-1)(2k+l+m)}{(2k+1)2k} \cos^{2j+1} \theta \right) \right)}_{l-m=1,3,5,\dots} \end{array} \right\}
 \tag{6}$$

with undetermined coefficients $a_{n,l}^{(m)}$ and $a_{n,l}^{(-m)}$ or $b_{n,l}^{(m)}$ and $b_{n,l}^{(-m)}$ satisfying the natural periodic condition $u(r, \theta + 2\pi, \phi + 2\pi) = u(r, \theta, \phi)$ is a subset of the exact solutions of Laplace equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \phi^2} = 0$$

The finite term summation in expression (6) can also be written as an infinite term summation. During the calculation process, the infinite summation will be interrupted, and the result will

still be the finite term summation,

$$u(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_{l=0}^{n_1} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\alpha_l r^l + \frac{\alpha_{-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \left(a_{n,l}^{(m)} \cos m\varphi + a_{n,l}^{(-m)} \sin m\varphi \right) \sin^m \theta \right) \right. \\ \left. \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l+m-2)(2k+l+m-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \cos^{2j}\theta \right) \right) \right\}_{l-m=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^{n_2} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\beta_l r^l + \frac{\beta_{-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \left(b_{n,l}^{(m)} \cos m\varphi + b_{n,l}^{(-m)} \sin m\varphi \right) \sin^m \theta \right) \right. \\ \left. \times \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l+m-1)(2k+l+m)}{(2k+1)2k} \cos^{2j+1}\theta \right) \right) \right\}_{l-m=1,3,5,\dots} \quad (7) \end{array} \right.$$

3 Special solution of Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum number

The concepts of direct product function and entanglement function were defined when introducing special entangled spherical harmonics earlier^[11]. The special entanglement function of zero magnetic quantum number is independent of traditional spherical harmonic functions, indicating that the traditional methods for solving spherical harmonic partial differential equations are not systematic, and their conclusions cannot be complete. The solution to the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation is inevitably only a local solution. Here, we first provide the traditional special solution for the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation corresponding to the special case of zero magnetic quantum numbers, and then present two different special solutions represented by two types of entangled spherical harmonics. The conclusions are expressed in the form of lemmas and theorems, respectively. Refer to the detailed proof in spherical harmonics, these lemmas and theorems do not need to be proven separately. But for the convenience of verification, traditional solutions and special entangled solutions will list some specific functions separately.

3.1 Complete Legendre Special Traditional Solution of Zero Magnetic Quantum Number Laplace Equation

When the magnetic quantum number $m = 0$, the traditional exact solution (7) of the Laplace equation's Dirichlet problem degenerates into a binary function containing only radial parameters r and angle θ , known as the Legendre special traditional solution of the Laplace equation's Dirichlet problem^[15, 16].

Lemma 2 (special traditional solution of Laplace equation Dirichlet problem): The special direct product function

$$u(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sum_{l=0}^{n_1} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\alpha_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\alpha_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \cos^{2j}\theta \right) \right) \right) \right\}_{l=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \sum_{l=0}^{n_2} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\beta_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\beta_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \cos^{2j+1}\theta \right) \right) \right) \right\}_{l=1,3,5,\dots} \quad (8) \end{array} \right.$$

with zero magnetic quantum numbers is a subset of the solutions of the Dirichlet problem

$$\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial u}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial u}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial \varphi^2} = 0$$

$$u(\theta, \varphi)|_{r=R} = f(\theta, \varphi)$$

for the ball Laplace equation.

The special traditional solution of the Dirichlet problem for the Laplace equation in the special case of zero magnetic quantum number mentioned above does not include angle ϕ . Table 3.1 lists the specific functions calculated from the special traditional solution (8) with $n_1 = n_2 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 6$ respectively. It can be verified that these functions satisfy the Laplace equation of football.

Table 3.1 Partial Legendre Special Traditional Solutions for the Dirichlet Problem of the Laplace Equation with Zero Magnetic Quantum Number

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_0(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \beta_{0,0} + \frac{\beta_{0,0}}{r} \\
 u_1(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \cos \theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{1,-1}}{r^2} + \alpha_{1,1}r \right) + \beta_{1,0} + \frac{\beta_{1,0}}{r} \\
 u_2(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \cos \theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{2,-1}}{r^2} + \alpha_{2,1}r \right) + \beta_{2,0} + \frac{\beta_{2,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\beta_{2,-2}}{r^3} + \beta_{2,2}r^2 \right) \\
 u_3(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos \theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{3,-1}}{r^2} + \alpha_{3,1}r \right) + \left(\cos \theta - \frac{5\cos^3 \theta}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha_{3,-3}}{r^4} + \alpha_{3,3}r^3 \right) \\ &+ \beta_{3,0} + \frac{\beta_{3,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\beta_{3,-2}}{r^3} + \beta_{3,2}r^2 \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 u_4(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos \theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{4,-1}}{r^2} + r\alpha_{4,1} \right) + \left(\cos \theta - \frac{5\cos^3 \theta}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha_{4,-3}}{r^4} + \alpha_{4,3}r^3 \right) \\ &+ \beta_{4,0} + \frac{\beta_{4,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\beta_{4,-2}}{r^3} + r^2\beta_{4,2} \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - 10\cos^2 \theta + \frac{35\cos^4 \theta}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\beta_{4,-4}}{r^5} + r^4\beta_{4,4} \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 u_5(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos \theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{5,-1}}{r^2} + \alpha_{5,1}r \right) + \left(\cos \theta - \frac{5\cos^3 \theta}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha_{5,-3}}{r^4} + \alpha_{5,3}r^3 \right) \\ &+ \left(\cos \theta - \frac{14}{3}\cos^3 \theta + \frac{21\cos^5 \theta}{5} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha_{5,-5}}{r^6} + \alpha_{5,5}r^5 \right) \\ &+ \beta_{5,0} + \frac{\beta_{5,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\beta_{5,-2}}{r^3} + \beta_{5,2}r^2 \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - 10\cos^2 \theta + \frac{35\cos^4 \theta}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\beta_{5,-4}}{r^5} + \beta_{5,4}r^4 \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 u_6(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos \theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{6,-1}}{r^2} + \alpha_{6,1}r \right) + \left(\cos \theta - \frac{5\cos^3 \theta}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha_{6,-3}}{r^4} + \alpha_{6,3}r^3 \right) \\ &+ \left(\cos \theta - \frac{14}{3}\cos^3 \theta + \frac{4}{15} \frac{63\cos^5 \theta}{4} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha_{6,-5}}{r^6} + \alpha_{6,5}r^5 \right) \\ &+ \beta_{6,0} + \frac{\beta_{6,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\beta_{6,-2}}{r^3} + \beta_{6,2}r^2 \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - 10\cos^2 \theta + \frac{35\cos^4 \theta}{3} \right) \left(\frac{\beta_{6,-4}}{r^5} + \beta_{6,4}r^4 \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - \frac{315}{15}\cos^2 \theta + \frac{945\cos^4 \theta}{15} - \frac{693\cos^6 \theta}{15} \right) \left(\frac{\beta_{6,-6}}{r^7} + \beta_{6,6}r^6 \right) \end{aligned} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

It can be seen that, except for $u_0(r, \theta, \phi)$, even in the special case where the magnetic quantum number is zero, the traditional special integral constant of the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace

equation increases with the increase of n , with $2n + 1 > 1$. Normalization conditions are far from sufficient to determine the specific function of such solutions. The traditional theory of using normalization conditions to determine the solution of the Laplace equation is not necessarily an inference.

3.2 The first type of special entangled solution for the zero magnetic quantum number Laplace equation

If $\cos \theta$ in the special traditional solution (8) of the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem is replaced with $\sin \theta \cos \phi$, a ternary entanglement function containing three spherical coordinate parameters r, θ, ϕ satisfying the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum number will be obtained, which is called the first type of special entanglement solution of the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem.

Theorem 1 (First Class Special Entangled Solution of Laplace Equation Dirichlet Problem)
The first type of special entanglement function

$$v(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p_1} \left(\left(\chi_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\chi_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} (\sin \theta \cos \varphi)^{2j} \right) \right)}_{l=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{p_2} \left(\left(\gamma_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\gamma_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} (\sin \theta \cos \varphi)^{2j+1} \right) \right)}_{l=1,3,5,\dots} \end{array} \right\} \quad (9)$$

with zero magnetic quantum numbers is a subset of the solutions to the Dirichlet problem

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial v}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial v}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial \varphi^2} = 0 \\ v(\theta, \varphi)|_{r=R} = f(\theta, \varphi) \end{aligned}$$

of the ball Laplace equation.

The first type of special entangled solution for the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum numbers mentioned above is not included in the Legendre special traditional solution (8). The shortcomings of the traditional theory of partial differential equations are obvious. Table 3.2 lists the specific functions calculated from the first type of special entanglement solution (9) with $p_1 = p_2 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 6$. It can be verified that these functions all satisfy the Laplace equation.

Table 3.2 Partial first type special entangled solutions of the zero magnetic quantum number Laplace equation Dirichlet problem

$$\begin{aligned} v_0(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \gamma_{0,0} + \frac{\gamma_{0,0}}{r} \\ v_1(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \cos \varphi \sin \theta \left(\frac{\chi_{1,-1}}{r^2} + \chi_{1,1} r \right) + \gamma_{1,0} + \frac{\gamma_{1,0}}{r} \\ v_2(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \cos \varphi \sin \theta \left(\frac{\chi_{2,-1}}{r^2} + \chi_{2,1} r \right) + \gamma_{2,0} + \frac{\gamma_{2,0}}{r} + (1 - 3 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\gamma_{2,-2}}{r^3} + \gamma_{2,2} r^2 \right) \\ v_3(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cos \varphi \sin \theta \left(\frac{\chi_{3,-1}}{r^2} + \chi_{3,1} r \right) + \left(\cos \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\chi_{3,-3}}{r^4} + \chi_{3,3} r^3 \right) \\ + \gamma_{3,0} + \frac{\gamma_{3,0}}{r} + (1 - 3 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\gamma_{3,-2}}{r^3} + \gamma_{3,2} r^2 \right) \end{array} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 v_4(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos \varphi \sin \theta \left(\frac{\chi_{4,-1}}{r^2} + \chi_{4,1} r \right) + \left(\cos \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\chi_{4,-3}}{r^4} + \chi_{4,3} r^3 \right) \\ &+ \gamma_{4,0} + \frac{\gamma_{4,0}}{r} + \left(1 - 3 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{4,-2}}{r^3} + \gamma_{4,2} r^2 \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - 10 \cos \varphi^2 \sin^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \cos^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{4,-4}}{r^5} + \gamma_{4,4} r^4 \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 v_5(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos \varphi \sin \theta \left(\frac{\chi_{5,-1}}{r^2} + \chi_{5,1} r \right) + \left(\cos \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\chi_{5,-3}}{r^4} + \chi_{5,3} r^3 \right) \\ &+ \left(\cos \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{14}{3} \cos^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta + \frac{21}{5} \cos^5 \varphi \sin^5 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\chi_{5,-5}}{r^6} + \chi_{5,5} r^5 \right) \\ &+ \gamma_{5,0} + \frac{\gamma_{5,0}}{r} + \left(1 - 3 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{5,-2}}{r^3} + \gamma_{5,2} r^2 \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - 10 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \cos^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{5,-4}}{r^5} + \gamma_{5,4} r^4 \right) \end{aligned} \right\} \\
 v_6(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\cos \varphi \sin \theta \left(\frac{\chi_{6,-1}}{r^2} + \chi_{6,1} r \right) + \left(\cos \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\chi_{6,-3}}{r^4} + \chi_{6,3} r^3 \right) \\ &+ \left(\cos \varphi \sin \theta - \frac{14}{3} \cos^3 \varphi \sin^3 \theta + \frac{21}{5} \cos^5 \varphi \sin^5 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\chi_{6,-5}}{r^6} + \chi_{6,5} r^5 \right) \\ &+ \gamma_{6,0} + \frac{\gamma_{6,0}}{r} + \left(1 - 3 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{6,-2}}{r^3} + \gamma_{6,2} r^2 \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - 10 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \cos^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{6,-4}}{r^5} + \gamma_{6,4} r^4 \right) \\ &+ \left(1 - 21 \cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + 63 \cos^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta - \frac{231}{5} \cos^6 \varphi \sin^6 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{6,-6}}{r^7} + \gamma_{6,6} r^6 \right) \end{aligned} \right\}
 \end{aligned}$$

Similar to Legendre’s special traditional solution, even in the special case where the magnetic quantum number is zero, except for $v_0(r, \theta, \phi)$, the integral constant of the first type of special entangled solution of the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem increases with the increase of p , with a total of $2p + 1 > 1$. Normalization conditions are far from sufficient to determine the specific function of such solutions. Moreover, traditional theories overlook the first type of special entangled solutions, and the conclusions described do not conform to the principle of existence and uniqueness of solutions.

3.3 The second type entangled special solution of the zero magnetic quantum number Laplace equation

Further replacing $\cos \theta$ with $\sin \phi \sin \theta$ in the special traditional solution (8) of the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem, another type of ternary function with three spherical coordinate parameters r, θ, ϕ that also satisfies the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum numbers is obtained, which is called the second type of special entangled solution of the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem.

Theorem 2 (Second type special entanglement solution of Laplace equation Dirichlet problem)

The second type special entanglement function

$$w(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \underbrace{\sum_{l=0}^{q_1} \left(\left(\eta_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\eta_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} (\sin \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j} \right) \right)}_{l=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \sum_{l=0}^{q_2} \left(\left(\mu_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\mu_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} (\sin \varphi \sin \theta)^{2j+1} \right) \right) \end{array} \right\} \quad (10)$$

for zero magnetic quantum numbers is a subset of the solutions to the Dirichlet problem

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos \theta}{\sin \theta} \frac{\partial w}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \varphi^2} &= 0 \\ w(\theta, \varphi)|_{r=R} &= f(\theta, \varphi) \end{aligned}$$

of the Laplace equation.

The second type of special entangled solution for the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum numbers mentioned above does not include the Legendre special traditional solution (8) and the first type of special entangled solution (9), which expands the Laplace equation solution. The new conclusion further illustrates the serious flaws in the traditional theory of partial differential equations. Table 3.3 lists the specific functions calculated from the second type of special entanglement solution (9) with $q_1 = q_2 = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 6$. It can be verified that these functions all satisfy the Laplace equation.

Table 3.3 Part of the second type of special entangled solution for the zero magnetic quantum number Laplace equation Dirichlet problem

$$\begin{aligned} w_0(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \mu_{0,0} + \frac{\mu_{0,0}}{r} \\ w_1(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \sin \theta \sin \varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{1,-1}}{r^2} + \eta_{1,1} r \right) + \mu_{1,0} + \frac{\mu_{1,0}}{r} \\ w_2(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \sin \theta \sin \varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{2,-1}}{r^2} + \eta_{2,1} r \right) + \mu_{2,0} + \frac{\mu_{2,0}}{r} + (1 - 3 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \left(\frac{\mu_{2,-2}}{r^3} + \mu_{2,2} r^2 \right) \\ w_3(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sin \theta \sin \varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{3,-1}}{r^2} + \eta_{3,1} r \right) + \left(\sin \theta \sin \varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \theta \sin^3 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{3,-3}}{r^4} + \eta_{3,3} r^3 \right) \\ + \mu_{3,0} + \frac{\mu_{3,0}}{r} + (1 - 3 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \left(\frac{\mu_{3,-2}}{r^3} + \mu_{3,2} r^2 \right) \end{array} \right\} \\ w_4(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sin \theta \sin \varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{4,-1}}{r^2} + \eta_{4,1} r \right) + \left(\sin \theta \sin \varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \theta \sin^3 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{4,-3}}{r^4} + \eta_{4,3} r^3 \right) \\ + \mu_{4,0} + \frac{\mu_{4,0}}{r} + (1 - 3 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \left(\frac{\mu_{4,-2}}{r^3} + \mu_{4,2} r^2 \right) \\ + \left(1 - 10 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \theta \sin^4 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{4,-4}}{r^5} + \mu_{4,4} r^4 \right) \end{array} \right\} \\ w_5(r, \theta, \varphi) &= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sin \theta \sin \varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{5,-1}}{r^2} + \eta_{5,1} r \right) + \left(\sin \theta \sin \varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \theta \sin^3 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{5,-3}}{r^4} + \eta_{5,3} r^3 \right) \\ + \left(\sin \theta \sin \varphi - \frac{14}{3} \sin^3 \theta \sin^3 \varphi + \frac{21}{5} \sin^5 \theta \sin^5 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{5,-5}}{r^6} + \eta_{5,5} r^5 \right) \\ + \mu_{5,0} + \frac{\mu_{5,0}}{r} + (1 - 3 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \left(\frac{\mu_{5,-2}}{r^3} + \mu_{5,2} r^2 \right) \\ + \left(1 - 10 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \theta \sin^4 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{5,-4}}{r^5} + \mu_{5,4} r^4 \right) \end{array} \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$w_6(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \sin \theta \sin \varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{6,-1}}{r^2} + \eta_{6,1} r \right) + \left(\sin \theta \sin \varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \theta \sin^3 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{6,-3}}{r^4} + \eta_{6,3} r^3 \right) \\ + \left(\sin \theta \sin \varphi - \frac{14}{3} \sin^3 \theta \sin^3 \varphi + \frac{21}{5} \sin^5 \theta \sin^5 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{6,-5}}{r^6} + \eta_{6,5} r^5 \right) \\ + \mu_{6,0} + \frac{\mu_{6,0}}{r} + (1 - 3 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \left(\frac{\mu_{6,-2}}{r^3} + \mu_{6,2} r^2 \right) \\ + \left(1 - 10 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \theta \sin^4 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{6,-4}}{r^5} + \mu_{6,4} r^4 \right) \\ + \left(1 - 21 \sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi + 63 \sin^4 \theta \sin^4 \varphi - \frac{231}{5} \sin^6 \theta \sin^6 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{6,-6}}{r^7} + r^6 \mu_{6,6} \right) \end{array} \right\}$$

The table is similar to the Legendre special traditional solution and the first type of special entangled solution. Except for $w_0(r, \theta, \phi)$, the integral constant of the second type of special entangled solution of the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem increases with the increase of q , with a total of $2q + 1 > 1$. Normalization conditions are far from sufficient to determine the specific function of this type of solution. Traditional theory neglects the first and second types of special entangled solutions, and the conclusions described do not conform to the principle of existence and uniqueness of solutions.

4 Complete special solution set of zero magnetic quantum number Laplace equation

Based on the two types of special entangled solutions of the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum numbers mentioned above, a preliminary conclusion can be drawn that the general solution of the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation described by traditional theory is far less than one-third of the total solution set. In mathematical terms, all functions that satisfy linear partial differential equations and meet the conditions for definite solutions are solutions to partial differential equations. The special traditional solution and two types of entangled solutions each form a solution basis for the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation. Any linear combination of solution bases is the general solution of the Laplace equation under the defined conditions. By superimposing three special functions (8), (9), and (10), the complete set of special solutions for the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum numbers is obtained.

Theorem 3 (Special General Solution of Laplace Equation Dirichlet Problem): The zero

magnetic quantum number mixed special entanglement function

$$\mathbb{U}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \left(\sum_{l=0}^{n_1} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\alpha_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\alpha_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} \cos^{2j}\theta \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ + \sum_{l=0}^{p_1} \left(\left(\chi_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\chi_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} (\sin\theta \cos\varphi)^{2j} \right) \right) \\ + \sum_{l=0}^{q_1} \left(\left(\eta_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\eta_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+2}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-2)(2k+l-1)}{2k(2k-1)} (\sin\varphi \sin\theta)^{2j} \right) \right) \\ \underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_{l=0,2,4,\dots} \\ + \left(\sum_{l=0}^{n_2} \left(\sum_{m=0}^l \left(\left(\beta_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\beta_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} \cos^{2j+1}\theta \right) \right) \right) \right) \\ + \sum_{l=0}^{p_2} \left(\left(\gamma_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\gamma_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} (\sin\theta \cos\varphi)^{2j+1} \right) \right) \\ + \sum_{l=0}^{q_2} \left(\left(\mu_{n,l} r^l + \frac{\mu_{n,-l}}{r^{l+1}} \right) \sum_{j=0}^{\frac{l+1}{2}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^j \frac{(2k-l-1)(2k+l)}{(2k+1)2k} (\sin\varphi \sin\theta)^{2j+1} \right) \right) \\ \underbrace{\hspace{10em}}_{l=1,3,5,\dots} \end{array} \right\} \quad (11)$$

is the complete set of special solutions for the Dirichlet problem

$$\frac{\partial^2 \mathbb{U}}{\partial r^2} + \frac{2}{r} \frac{\partial \mathbb{U}}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{\partial^2 \mathbb{U}}{\partial \theta^2} + \frac{\cos\theta}{\sin\theta} \frac{\partial \mathbb{U}}{\partial \theta} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2 \sin^2 \theta} \frac{\partial^2 \mathbb{U}}{\partial \varphi^2} = 0$$

$$\mathbb{U}(\theta, \varphi)|_{r=R} = f(\theta, \varphi)$$

of the zero magnetic quantum number ball Laplace equation.

The complete special solution set of the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem with zero magnetic quantum numbers consists of $n_1 + n_2 + p_1 + p_2 + q_1 + q_2 + 4$ undetermined integral constants, which cannot be determined by normalization conditions. Therefore, the specific form of the solution to the Laplace equation Dirichlet problem cannot be determined. In (11), take $n_1 = 1$, $n_2 = 2$, $p_1 = 3$, $p_2 = 4$, $q_1 = 5$, $q_2 = 6$, the results obtained are as follows

$$\mathbb{U}_{\leq 6}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cos\theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{n,-1}}{r^2} + \alpha_{n,1} r \right) + \beta_{n,0} + \frac{\beta_{n,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2\theta) \left(\frac{\beta_{n,-2}}{r^3} + \beta_{n,2} r^2 \right) \\ + \gamma_{n,0} + \frac{\gamma_{n,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2\varphi \sin^2\theta) \left(\frac{\gamma_{n,-2}}{r^3} + \gamma_{n,2} r^2 \right) \\ + \left(1 - 10\cos^2\varphi \sin^2\theta + \frac{35}{3} \cos^4\varphi \sin^4\theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{n,-4}}{r^5} + \gamma_{n,4} r^4 \right) \\ + \sin\theta \sin\varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{n,-1}}{r^2} + \eta_{n,1} r \right) + \left(\sin\theta \sin\varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3\theta \sin^3\varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{n,-3}}{r^4} + \eta_{n,3} r^3 \right) \\ + \left(\sin\theta \sin\varphi - \frac{14}{3} \sin^3\theta \sin^3\varphi + \frac{21}{5} \sin^5\theta \sin^5\varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{n,-5}}{r^6} + \eta_{n,5} r^5 \right) \\ + \mu_{n,0} + \frac{\mu_{n,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\sin^2\theta \sin^2\varphi) \left(\frac{\mu_{n,-2}}{r^3} + \mu_{n,2} r^2 \right) \\ + \left(1 - 10\sin^2\theta \sin^2\varphi + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4\theta \sin^4\varphi \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{n,-4}}{r^5} + \mu_{n,4} r^4 \right) \\ + \left(1 - 21\sin^2\theta \sin^2\varphi + 63\sin^4\theta \sin^4\varphi - \frac{231}{5} \sin^6\theta \sin^6\varphi \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{n,-6}}{r^7} + \mu_{n,6} r^6 \right) \\ + \cos\varphi \sin\theta \left(\frac{\chi_{n,-1}}{r^2} + \chi_{n,1} r \right) + \left(\cos\varphi \sin\theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3\varphi \sin^3\theta \right) \left(\frac{\chi_{n,-3}}{r^4} + \chi_{n,3} r^3 \right) \end{array} \right\} \quad (12)$$

In (11), take $n_1=3, n_2=1, p_1=2, p_2=6, q_2=5$, The results obtained are as follows

$$U_{\leq 6}(r, \theta, \varphi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cos \theta \left(\frac{\alpha_{n,-1}}{r^2} + r\alpha_{n,1} \right) + \left(\cos \theta - \frac{5}{3} \cos^3 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\alpha_{n,-3}}{r^4} + r^3 \alpha_{n,3} \right) \\ + \beta_{n,0} + \frac{\beta_{n,0}}{r} + \gamma_{n,0} + \frac{\gamma_{n,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta) \left(\frac{\gamma_{n,-2}}{r^3} + r^2 \gamma_{n,2} \right) \\ + \left(1 - 10\cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + \frac{35}{3} \cos^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{n,-4}}{r^5} + r^4 \gamma_{n,4} \right) \\ + \left(1 - 21\cos^2 \varphi \sin^2 \theta + 63\cos^4 \varphi \sin^4 \theta - \frac{231}{5} \cos^6 \varphi \sin^6 \theta \right) \left(\frac{\gamma_{n,-6}}{r^7} + r^6 \gamma_{n,6} \right) \\ + \sin \theta \sin \varphi \left(\frac{\eta_{n,-1}}{r^2} + r\eta_{n,1} \right) + \left(\sin \theta \sin \varphi - \frac{5}{3} \sin^3 \theta \sin^3 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\eta_{n,-3}}{r^4} + r^3 \eta_{n,3} \right) \\ + \mu_{n,0} + \frac{\mu_{n,0}}{r} + (1 - 3\sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi) \left(\frac{\mu_{n,-2}}{r^3} + r^2 \mu_{n,2} \right) + \cos \varphi \sin \theta \left(\frac{\chi_{n,-1}}{r^2} + r\chi_{n,1} \right) \\ + \left(1 - 10\sin^2 \theta \sin^2 \varphi + \frac{35}{3} \sin^4 \theta \sin^4 \varphi \right) \left(\frac{\mu_{n,-4}}{r^5} + r^4 \mu_{n,4} \right) \end{array} \right\} \quad (13)$$

According to Theorem 3, it is possible to write functions similar to (12) and (13) that satisfy the Laplace equation and contain arbitrary terms. After combining similar terms, there are sufficient uncertain integral constants. Therefore, the specific functional form of the special entangled solution of the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum number is uncertain.

The college system enables successive generations of students to proficiently memorize the solutions of the Laplace equation represented by the function defined by the retraction symbol in textbooks, but the hidden problems behind those solutions cannot be discovered, which reflects the shortcomings of academic education. Society needs cloned talents, but scientific problems also require independent research and creation. Even a specific example of the solution to the Dirichlet problem of the Laplace equation with zero magnetic quantum numbers is much more complex than the seemingly perfect universal form in memory. If different solutions such as Laplace's equation have received special attention in history and more people are accustomed to manual verification, then the theory of partial differential equations will not hide numerous significant flaws in principles that are difficult to discover like the established traditional forms.

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Many details of the Laplace equation solution cannot be reflected by formal standard solutions, but can be inferred from various concrete solutions constructed. Using Mathematica to verify (12), the format and results that satisfy the Laplace equation should be

$$\frac{D \left[(r^2 D[U, r]), r \right]}{\frac{1}{\sin[\theta]} D[\sin[\theta] D[U, \theta], \theta] + \frac{1}{(\sin[\theta])^2} D[D[U, \varphi], \varphi]} = -1 \quad (14)$$

However, the specific form of the Laplace equation solution with zero magnetic quantum numbers (12) cannot be determined. All the conclusions of theories described by Laplace equations are only non inevitable inferences hidden under special descriptive techniques, with very low confidence.

5 Conclusion

The Laplace equation is the simplest second-order homogeneous linear partial differential equation with symmetry, but its solution is the most complex. This only discusses the very special case of zero magnetic quantum numbers, but the description of the problem and conclusions needed are already cumbersome enough. As for the general case where the magnetic quantum number is not zero, the generalized entangled spherical harmonic function can provide a richer and more accurate solution to the Laplace equation. There seems to be no exhaustive method to find all solutions to the Laplace equation that are not described by existing theories and differ from the latest discoveries. Whether in the field of mathematics or applied science^[17], the conclusions of Laplace equation solutions advocated by traditional theories and the descriptions of natural phenomena are obviously unrealistic.

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